

DESERT AND SEMI-DESERT PHYTOCENOSES OF THE MIL PLAIN: IMPLICATIONS FOR WINTER PASTURE MANAGEMENT**Asadova A. Kamala***Baku State University, Faculty of Biology,
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Baku, Azerbaijan*<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6531-3444>**Abstract**

At the present stage, the efficient use of phytocenoses or vegetation cover of natural winter pastures is of particular relevance. As a result of our research, the phytocenological structure, species composition, productivity, and forage capacity of characteristic formations occurring in various vegetation types of the Mil Plain have been studied. Based on these investigations, recommendations for the rational use and improvement of the studied phytocenoses have been developed.

Keywords: type, formation, association, dominant, subdominant, phytocenosis

Study Area and Methods

Geobotanical studies were conducted in several areas of the Mil Plain, mainly within the administrative boundaries of the Agjabadi District, on winter pastures during April-May and November-December of 2016–2017.

The diversity of relief, soil, and climatic conditions in the winter pastures of the study area has contributed to the formation of natural phytocenoses [2]. Sample plots of the *Artemisietum-Salsolosum* (wormwood–saltwort) formation, characteristic of semi-desert vegetation, were selected as research objects.

Geobotanical investigations were carried out in accordance with standard methodological guidelines, including the assessment of species composition, structure, productivity, nutritional value (forage quality), and pasture capacity of the phytocenoses [1,5,11,12,14,18].

The studied semi-desert phytocenoses were recorded on saline, solonchic meadow-gray, and gray-meadow soils [1,5,9,10]. Along the banks of the Kura River, shrub communities (*Tamarixeta ramosissima* Lebed.) and sparse tugai forests occur on meadow-forest (tugai) soils.

Numerous herbarium specimens collected from desert, semi-desert, meadow-depression, and wetland vegetation were identified according to “Flora of Azerbaijan.” Plant nomenclature follows S.K. Cherepanov, as well as V.C. Hajiyevev and T.E. Gasimova [6,17,19].

The climate of the area belongs to the semi-desert, moderately warm, and dry steppe type [4]. The mean annual air temperature is 14.0°C, and the annual precipitation averages 332 mm. Climatic conditions directly affect the structure, productivity, forage quality, and grazing period of the vegetation cover.

Semi-desert vegetation represented by the wormwood–saltwort formation is mainly distributed on gray-meadow soils.

Results and Discussion

A total of 21 species of higher flowering plants were recorded in the species composition of the *Artemisietum-Salsolosum* formation. These include 2 shrub species (9.5%), 1 semi-shrub (4.8%), 2 subshrubs (9.5%), 6 perennial herbs (28.6%), and 10 annual herbs (47.6%).

According to ecological analysis, the flora is represented by 7 xerophytes (33.3%), 7 halophytes (33.3%), 3 mesophytes (14.3%), and 4 mesoxerophytes (19.1%).

The dominant species of the phytocenosis is *Salsola dendroides* Pall. with an abundance of 3–4 points, while the subdominant species is *Artemisia lurchiana* Web. with an abundance of 2–3 points. Structurally, the vegetation cover consists of two layers: the first layer is formed by *Salsola* shrubs, and the second layer by *Artemisia*.

Geobotanical description

Species composition and structure of the wormwood-saltwort formation (with the dominance of *Salsola dendroides* Pall. as the dominant species)

S/s	Biomorphic species	Ecological groups	Abundance (with score)	Layering and average height (sm)	Phenological phases
1	2	3	4	5	6
	Shrubs				
1	Tamarix ramosissima Lebed.	mezoxerophyte	1-2	I (150)	Flow.
2	Caragana arberoscens Lam.	mezoxerophyte	1	II (90)	Flow.
	Semishrubs				
3	Salsola dendroides Pall.	mezoxerophyte	3-4	II (70)	veg
	Subshrubs				
4	Kalidium caspicum (L.) Ungo-Sternb.	halophyte	1-2	II (50)	veg
5	Capparis herbacea Willd.	xerophyte	1	III (20)	Flow.
	Perennials				
6	Artemisia lerchiana Web.	xerophyte	2-3	III (30)	veg
7	Limonium meyeri (Boiss.) O.Kuntze	halophyte	1-2	II (45)	Flow.
8	Glycyrrhiza glabra L.	mezoxerophyte	1	II (70)	Flow.
9	Cynodon dactylon (L.) Pers.	mezophyte	1	III (30)	Flow.
10	Trapogon graminifolius DC.	mezophyte	1	III (20)	Flow.
11	Aeluropus reflexiaristata (Nevski) Nevski	mezophyte	1	III (15)	Flow.
12	Petrosimonia brachiata (Pall.) Bunge	halophyte	1-2	III (25)	veg
13	Bromus japonicus Thunb.	xerophyte	1-2	III (10)	Flow.
14	Xanthium strumarium L.	xerophyte	1	II (40)	Flow.
15	Hordeum leporinum Link. Phleum	xerophyte	1	II (35)	Flow.
16	puloides (L.) Karst.	xerophyte	1	III (30)	Flow.
17	Lolium rigidum Gaudin.	xerophyte	1	III (25)	Flow.
18	Eremopyrum orientale (L.) Jaub. et Spach.	halophyte	1	III (20)	Flow.
19	Psylliostachus halospicata (Willd.) Nevski	halophyte	1	III (15)	veg
20	Climocoptera halocrassa (Bieb.) Botsch.	halophyte	1	III (10)	veg
21	Gamanthus pilosus (Pall.) Bunge.	halophyte	1	III (5)	Flow.

The total projective cover varies between 60 and 80%. The average height of the herbaceous layer is 30–40 cm.

The average productivity of the wormwood-saltwort formation, calculated based on dry biomass, was determined to be 8.2 centners per hectare.

In the flat areas of the Mil Plain, desert and semi-desert vegetation has been subjected to degradation and salinization due to anthropogenic and technogenic impacts, as well as excessive grazing pressure. Based on the results of geobotanical investigations presented in this study, measures for the rational use and improvement of phytocenoses of the Mil Plain are recommended.

The implementation of these scientifically grounded measures will contribute to the conservation and protection of winter pasture vegetation in the Mil Plain region.

Conclusion

The desert and semi-desert phytocenoses of the Mil Plain are characterized by a complex species composition and clear structural differentiation formed under specific soil-climatic conditions. The dominance of *Salsola dendroides* and *Artemisia lerchiana* determines the ecological stability and forage value of the wormwood-saltwort formation. However, increasing anthropogenic pressure has led to degradation processes in

winter pastures. Rational management and improvement measures based on geobotanical assessments are essential for the sustainable use and long-term conservation of these phytocenoses.

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